

8T –Curvature Spikes Amplitudes

"I know what it means to know something." Richard Feynman.

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series in the less familiar pi representation, it is possible to construct new meaning to that equation. In particular, it is possible to classify the pi part of the net variation to the area of the net curvature wave, and the rest of the term to the energy or the height of the spike. In physical meaning that could be the analogy of the amplitude.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

In page sixty six of the 8T thesis we have presented a possible variation of the primorial, replacing the electron by pi, to derive it is imperfect circle close to pi. We presented additional variation, with the net variation as demonstrated in the page below.

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (\pi) \right) + N_V$$

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) : (24 + (\pi)) + 3 : (120 + (\pi)) + 5 : (840 + (\pi)) + 7 \dots$$

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) : (24 + (\pi)) + \pi : (120 + (\pi)) + (\pi + 1.82) : (840 + (\pi)) + (2\pi + 0.716)..$$

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. we have analyzed the fact that each element in the series is weaker than the preceding to the aspiring zero ration of net to total. This is relevant because the idea one would like to present in this paper is the following: the pi terms of the net variation are representing the area of propagation and the numerical terms of the net variation such as 1.82, 0.716., are representing the amplitude, the height of the spike. As we keep developing the series the amplitude gets weaker and weaker, i.e. lower and the area of propagation gets wider. Highest amplitude (from the second and above to avoid the complexity of the first term) is correlative to the second term. We can make it rigorous:

$$\eta_n \pi \rightarrow \theta; \eta \in [0, \mathbb{R}]$$

$$N_V - \eta \pi \rightarrow E_n;$$

The result of this idea will vary the primorial in the following way:

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) : (24 + (\pi)) + \pi : (120 + (\pi)) + (\eta_n \pi + E_n) : (840 + (\pi)) + (\eta_{n+1} \pi + E_{n+1})..$$

For the weak interaction the amplitude and the area are embedded in the term π , the classification is more vivid from the coupling term of the Electric and above. As the series develop we can see the inverse relation among the two components:

$$\eta_n \pi \rightarrow \infty$$

$$E_n \rightarrow 0$$

$$n \rightarrow \infty$$

Such a classification is beneficial, as we would like to insert and include vital features as amplitudes and spikes areas, which are fundamental importance in physical theories. The terms were not possible to include in net variation, as it contain only one term and certainly not possible to include in spin representation. For those reasons, we can use the pi representation which trade off the accuracy but allows us to expand the scope of the 8T to new horizons.

Alternatively, in much more accurate representation and beautiful visualization of the idea of the spike amplitude and area, is the water ripple illustration:

As time goes by, the amplitude will decrease lower and lower height and the circular areas will get larger and increase infinity, similar to what the primordial is indicating. This pi representation allows us to vividly observe the wave features of the primordial; the difference is that instead of water wave we have diverging curvature on the metric tensor, which is isomorphic to prime numbers or one. The prime number feature is indicating the independency of those waves and lack of dependency on matter. The aspiring zero spike is an indicator to the weakness of interaction from term to term, it can also be used to explain the particle wave-duality, the top of the spike can be viewed by an observer as a particle, while at the same time the pi multiples are the part which represents the waves. The complication is that the spike should travel with the wave itself, and that is not the case in the water illustration. However, the key point is that the pi representation allows us to make a classification according to ever-increasing spike area and ever-decreasing spikes height, which could be an analogue to wave amplitude and wave propagation in space that fills space overtime.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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